

Valve control system on a venturi to control FiO_2 a portable ventilator with fuzzy logic method based on microcontroller

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ABSTRACT

The results of several studies for portable ventilators state that it is difficult to regulate oxygen levels of fraction of inspired oxygen (FiO_2) that are in accordance with what is needed directly during the implementation of oxygen therapy. Some portable ventilators cannot set the FiO_2 , so the ventilators work with a fixed FiO_2 . To overcome this problem, medical oxygen with a level of 100% is lowered by mixing with free air with an oxygen content of about 40%. Mixing is carried out using a venturi with a large/wide hole that can be adjusted using a slated disk rotated by a direct current motor. The rotation control method uses Mamdani's fuzzy logic. The results of clinically lab-scale testing show that the fuzzy logic control system is able to control the average error pressure of 10.3%, better when compared to the on-off control method, which is 14.5%. The fuzzy logic method is able to increase the accuracy of FiO_2 on a portable ventilator.

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1. INTRODUCTION

A mechanical ventilator is a positive or negative pressure breathing apparatus that produces controlled air flow in the patient's airway so that it is able to maintain ventilation and oxygen delivery for a long time. The mechanical breathing apparatus acts as a substitute for the function of the chest pump that is experiencing fatigue or failure [1]–[3]. There are many techniques and models of tools that can be used in oxygen therapy (O_2) which each have advantages and disadvantages. The selection of techniques and tools to be used is largely determined by the condition of the patient who will be given oxygen (O_2) therapy [4].

The techniques and tools that will be used in the administration of oxygen (O_2) therapy should meet the following criteria [2], [5]–[11],

- Able to regulate the concentration or fraction of oxygen (FiO_2) of inspiring air.
- Does not cause the accumulation of carbon dioxide (CO_2).
- Resistance to minimal breathing.
- Economical and efficient in the use of oxygen (O_2).

Due to the importance of oxygen therapy for several treatment therapies, the lack of availability and high availability of ventilators that can regulate oxygen levels in the air [12]. This study is designed an accurate and stability control of the oxygen concentration value or Fraction of Inspired Oxygen (FiO_2) that can be applied to a portable mechanical ventilator at a relatively low price. The ventilator can be used in public medical services other than in the ICU room of a large hospital.

2. METHOD

The architectural design in this study was designed in several parts, namely; oxygen level, oxygen mixing system, Maxtec Max-250 sensor as oxygen content detector, microcontroller data processing, fuzzy logic control system control, and display. The object taken in this study was the oxygen level in the breathing circuit of a ventilator. The analog signal from the oxygen sensor enters the analog to digital converter (ADC) microcontroller to convert the signal from the analog signal into a digital signal and the data will enter the Fuzzy logic oxygen level control software. The result of the control system will regulate the variable magnitude of the opening which will regulate the amount of air entering the mixing venturi [13], to obtain the oxygen concentration in accordance with the settings, then the processing results will be displayed in an LCD.

The prototype of the system in this study was designed using Arduino Mega as the main microcontroller. Figure 1 has shown the diagram of the equipment block as a whole [14]. Figure 2 has shown the process of air mixing due to pressure differences. The process of mixing oxygen can be carried out using the principle of continuity and Bernoulli's equation [14], [15]. Figure 3 have shown Bernaulli's principle [13].

Figure 1. Ventilator oxygen concentration control system model

Figure 2. The process of air mixing due to pressure differences

Figure 3. Bernoulli principle [13]

Information,

- P1: Pressure 1
- V1: Volume 1
- A2: Cross-sectional area 2
- A1: Cross-sectional area 1
- P2: Pressure 2
- V2: Volume 2
- P3: Free air pressure

the number of times that come in and the time that comes out is the same [16], [17].

$$Q = \frac{Volume}{time} \tag{1}$$

The volume of fluid passing through the cross section of the pipe in a certain interval of time (ΔT) can be expressed as the product of the cross-sectional area of the pipe (A) multiplied by the distance the fluid travels (Δx) [16], [17]. Where ($\Delta T/\Delta t$) there is a substitution of the velocity of the fluid V . Therefore, we can calculate the volumetric flow rate of the fluid simply by measuring the velocity of the fluid. Speed measurements can be achieved by applying the concepts discussed above to pipes with varying cross sections as shown in Figure 2. By making a venturi that has a hole that can be adjusted in area, we can adjust the amount of space air that will enter and mix so that the oxygen concentration could be controlled. Figure 4 has shown a space air hole area regulating system design. A fuzzy-controlled direct current motor will rotate the scuffed disk [18]–[20]. The amount of air entering depends on the rotation of the disk.

$$Q = \frac{A \times \Delta x}{\Delta t} = AV \tag{2}$$

$$\Delta P = P_1 - P_2 = \frac{1}{2}\rho(V_2^2 - V_1^2) \tag{3}$$

$$\rho A_1 V_1 \Delta t = \rho A_2 V_2 \Delta t \tag{4}$$

Figure 4. Space air hole area regulating system

2.1. Fuzzy logic method and defuzzification

The Fuzzy logic method used in this study is Mamdani. Mamdani is also referred to as the MAX-MIN method [21], [22]. To find out the output through 4 steps: First, forming membership function of Fuzzy sets; Second, applying the implications of Mamdani functions (rules) using the Min Implications function; Third, Mamdani's rule preparation can use 3 composition rules, namely: max, additive, or; Fourth, affirming (defuzzied) the result of the composition set, needs to be interpreted into a crisp value as the final result.

The fuzzy control system is designed with two input variables (Error and delta error) as well as one output variable (Aperture time). The input error variable is the specified oxygen level minus the measured oxygen level. The delta error input variable is the difference between the current error and the previous error. Figure 5(a) has shown error variable membership function and Figure 5(b) has shown delta error membership

function. Figure 6 as shown the output variable of aperture time is the length of the rotating chamber air gap disk with membership function.

Figure 5. Fuzzy membership function. (a) Error variable and (b) Delta error variable

Note:

EN: Negative error; EZ: Error zero; EP: Positive error; EN: Negatif error; Zero error; EP: Positif error

Figure 6. Rotating old variable membership function

2.2. Inference model

In the functional form, the degree of membership is expressed as a certain mathematical function. Degree of membership of each element requires calculation. Mamdani fuzzy inference system operation: First is to determine a set of fuzzy rules. The input membership function is used as fuzzification. secondly, fuzzy operations are performed by combining inputs that are fuzzified according to fuzzy rules to form fuzzy operations. The mathematical function that is usually used is the trapezoidal function. Following is error variable membership function.

$$\mu_{EN}(X) = \begin{cases} 1 & ; x \leq -25 \\ \frac{-x}{25} & ; -25 < x < 0 \\ 0 & ; x \geq 0 \end{cases} \tag{5}$$

$$\mu_{EZ}(X) = \begin{cases} 0 & ; x \leq -25 \text{ or } x \geq 25 \\ \frac{x+25}{25} & ; -25 < x < 0 \\ \frac{25-x}{10025} & ; 0 < x < 25 \\ 1 & ; x = 0 \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

$$\mu_{EP} = \begin{cases} 0 & ; x \leq 0 \text{ or } x \geq 50 \\ \frac{25-x}{25} & ; 0 < x < 25 \\ \frac{25-x}{25} & ; 25 < x < 50 \\ 1 & ; x = 25 \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

Variable delta error membership function,

$$\mu_{DK}(X) = \begin{cases} 1 & ; x = 0 \\ \frac{10-x}{10} & ; 0 < x < 10 \\ 0 & ; x \geq 10 \end{cases} \tag{8}$$

$$\mu_{DS}(X) = \begin{cases} 0 & ; x \leq 0 \text{ or } x \geq 20 \\ \frac{x}{10} & ; 0 < x < 10 \\ \frac{10-x}{10} & ; 10 < x < 20 \\ 1 & ; x = 10 \end{cases} \tag{9}$$

$$\mu_{DB}(X) = \begin{cases} 0 & ; x \leq 10 \\ \frac{10-x}{10} & ; 10 < x < 20 \\ 1 & ; x \geq 20 \end{cases} \tag{10}$$

The fuzzy processing stage is based on a set of logical rules in the form of an IF-THEN statement, where the IF part is called the "antecedent" and the THEN part is called the "consequence" [23]. This research fuzzy control system has 9 rules. Table 1 has shown the fuzzy base role mode created for the control system.

Table 1. The fuzzy base role mode

Rule	Error	ΔError	Output
1	IF EP AND DK	THEN PB	
2	IF EP AND DS	THEN PB	
3	IF EP AND DB	THEN PK	
7	IF EN AND DK	THEN NB	
8	IF EN AND DS	THEN NB	
9	IF EN AND DB	THEN NK	

2.3. Defuzzification

The next stage is defuzzification which converts the fuzzy output to crisp according to the predetermined affiliate function [24]. If the oxygen level has not reached the specified one, the controlling system will rotate the splattered disk in such a way that it can be achieved. The input of the defuzzification process is a fuzzy set obtained from the composition of fuzzy rules, while the resulting output is a firm real number. So that if given a fuzzy set in a certain range, a certain firm value can be taken as a value to rotate the motor clockwise or counterclockwise with the duration of the DC motor flame. The longer the motor rotates, the larger the opening of the free air valve. The defuzzification used is the centroid method (Composite moment), a crisp solution obtained by taking the center point of the fuzzy area [25].

Examples of Defuzzification processes,
 Error = 20 and delta error 17,

$$\mu_{EP}(20) = \frac{20}{25} = 0.8$$

$$\mu_{DK}(17) = \frac{17-10}{10} = 0.7$$

$$\mu_{DB}(17) = \frac{20-17}{20-10} = 0.2$$

Rule1: If **EP** and **DK** then **PB**

$$\alpha - Predicate_1 = \mu_{EP}(20) \cap \mu_{DK}(17)$$

$$\alpha - Predicate_1 = \min (\mu_{EP}(20); \mu_{DK}(17))$$

$$\alpha - Predicate_1 = \min(0.8; 0.7)$$

$$\alpha - Predicate_1 = 0.7$$

Rule2: If **EP** and **DB** the **PK**

$$\alpha - Predicate_2 = \mu_{EP}(20) \cap \mu_{DB}(17)$$

$$\alpha - Predicate_2 = \min (\mu_{EP}(20); \mu_{DK}(17))$$

$$\alpha - Predicate_2 = \min(0.2; 0.7)$$

$$\alpha - Predicate_2 = 0.2$$

the next stage is used the maximum method, which is to take the maximum values from the minimum values in the previous stage. Figure 7 has shown compositional result area.

Figure 7. Compositional result area

Looking for the value of t_1 :

$$\frac{t_1 - 0}{5 - 0} = 0.7$$

Then it can be calculated $t_1 = 3.5$. In the same way t_2 and t_3 can be calculated, that is, $t_2 = 6.5$ and $t_3 = 9$. Membership curve $\mu_1(z)$,

$$\mu(Z) = \begin{cases} 0 & ; x \leq 0 \\ \frac{z}{3.5} & ; 0 < x < 3.5 \\ 0.7 & ; x \geq 3.5 \end{cases}$$

Calculating the moment M_1 ,

$$M_1 = \int_0^{3.5} \frac{z}{3.5} z dz = 4.08$$

Calculating the area of A_1 ,

$$A_1 = \int_0^{3.5} \frac{z}{23.5} dz = 1.75$$

In the same way we can calculate M_2, M_3, M_4, A_2, A_3 and A_4 , $M_2 = 10.5; M_3 = 42.39; M_4 = 14.4; A_2 = 2.1; A_3 = 7.68; A_4 = 1.2$.

Centroid Defuzzification:

$$Z^* = \frac{\int \mu(z)z dz}{\int \mu(z) dz} = \frac{M_1+M_2+M_3+M_4}{A_1+A_2+A_3+A_4} \tag{11}$$

$$Z^* = \frac{4.08+10.5+42.39+14.4}{1.75+2.1+7.68+1.2} = 5.6$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FiO₂ testing is carried out at the Testing and Calibration of Clinical Laboratory, Semarang. The test equipment used is a Fluke brand ventilator calibration device with the Mobile VT type. The test uses a breathing circuit and artificial lungs (test lung) to simulate the actual patient. The first test was carried out using an on-off control system. System control is carried out without a reverse value as feedback. Testing is performed repeatedly with different set values of points. It starts with a set of 40% to 100% points with an interval of 5%. Measurements with a calibration tool are carried out 5 times. The result of the average value of the oxygen level is read on the calibration tool compared to the value on the set of points. After testing, the results listed in Table 2 are obtained. The difference between the specified value (set of points) and the average value read on the measuring instrument is compared. The difference in values that occur (errors) for each set of points is made on average, which is 14.5%.

The next step is ventilator testing using the Fuzzy Logic method. System control is carried out by entering values that read as feedback. Testing is performed repeatedly with different set values of points. It starts with a set of points 20% to 100% with an interval of 5%. Measurements with a calibration tool are carried out 5 times. The result of the average value of the oxygen level is read on the calibration tool compared to the value on the set of points. After testing, the results listed in Table 1 are obtained. Figure 8 has shown the venturi regulates oxygen levels design. Table 2 has shown F_iO₂ on-off control test result and Table 3 has shown fuzzy methode.

Table 2. Test results on-off method

No	Set Point	Measured Value (%)					Ave-rage	Error
1	40	35.2	34.1	36.3	46.2	50.6	40.5	1.2
2	45	44.7	44	47.3	38.5	38.5	42.6	5.3
3	50	59.4	55	62.7	46.2	59.4	56.5	13.1
4	55	64.9	66	59.4	62.7	51.7	60.9	10.8
5	60	66	59.4	70.4	58.3	73.7	65.6	9.3
6	65	73.7	60.5	77	81.4	75.9	73.7	13.4
7	70	67.1	69.3	82.5	75.9	74.8	73.9	5.6
8	75	77	88	83.6	86.9	90.2	85.1	13.5
9	80	83.8	99	85.8	80.3	84.7	86.7	8.4
10	85	94.5	97.9	90.2	90.3	90.2	92.6	9.0
11	90	99.3	96.8	98.4	96.8	96.8	97.6	8.5
12	95	98.3	98.6	98.4	93	90.4	95.7	0.8
13	100	95.9	98.4	99.4	98.6	94.5	97.4	2.6
							Average	14.5%

Figure 8. Venturi regulates oxygen levels

Table 3. Test result fuzzy method

No	Set Point	Measured Value (%)					Ave-rage	Error
1	40	42.9	42.9	42.6	38.6	41.4	41.7	4.2
2	45	46.4	44.5	47.5	42.6	46.4	45.5	1.1
3	50	53.4	48.9	48.5	51.3	53.3	51.1	2.2
4	55	50.5	52.3	57.5	54.3	56.3	54.2	1.5
5	60	58.5	58.3	58.6	63.5	63.2	60.4	0.7
6	65	64.5	66.4	67.5	66.7	66.6	66.3	2.1
7	70	69.4	72.4	74.3	73.5	69.5	71.8	2.6
8	75	77.5	68.4	74.6	74.5	78.5	74.7	0.4
9	80	80.8	78.8	79.6	82.4	85.3	81.4	1.7
10	85	86.3	87.6	86.4	84.5	87.4	86.4	1.7
11	90	93.5	89.5	92.2	88.9	93.4	91.5	1.7
12	95	98.3	94.5	93.6	96.4	98.9	96.3	1.4
13	100	100	99.5	100	97.5	95.9	98.6	1.4
							Average	2.1%

Figure 9 has shown the deviation that occurs in the on-off control system. The number of errors/deviations that occur is randomly valued between 0.8% and 13.6%. Figure 10 has shown that the deviation that occurs is relatively smaller, namely in the fuzzy control system. The number of errors/deviations that occur is randomly valued between 0.8% and 13.6%. The number of errors/deviations that occur is randomly valued between 0.4% and 4.2%.

Figure 9. Test results on-off method

Figure 10. Test result fuzzy method

4. CONCLUSION

The arrangement of the size of the venturi hole so that free air can enter can be used to regulate the oxygen concentration on a ventilator. The Fuzzy method control system is very well applied in a ventilator to control the stability of FiO_2 oxygen levels that have been predetermined at a certain amount by the user. The error for FiO_2 control is 2.1% with a minimum set point of 40%. The manufacture of portable mechanical ventilators that can be regulated by FiO_2 can be done domestically relatively easily and cheaply, so that they can be used en masse in emergency hospitals when there is a pandemic of diseases that attack the health of the human respiratory system.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. Fludger and A. Klein, "Portable ventilators," *Continuing Education in Anaesthesia, Critical Care and Pain*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 199–203, 2008, doi: 10.1093/bjaceaccp/mkn039.
- [2] Freescale Semiconductor, "Ventilator/respirator hardware and software design specification," *Ventilator/Respirator Hardware and Software Design Specification*, Rev. 0, 11/2011, p. 77, 2011, [Online]. Available: <https://docplayer.net/10921139-Ventilator-respirator-hardware-and-software-design-specification.html>.
- [3] E. L'Her, A. Roy, and N. Marjanovic, "Bench-test comparison of 26 emergency and transport ventilators," *Critical Care*, vol. 18, no. 5, 2014, doi: 10.1186/s13054-014-0506-0.
- [4] G. Hardavella, I. Karampinis, A. Frille, K. Sreter, and I. Rousalova, "Oxygen devices and delivery systems," *Breathe*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. e108–e116, 2019, doi: 10.1183/20734735.0204-2019.
- [5] M. Ferrer *et al.*, "Ventilator-associated pneumonia and PaO₂/FIO₂ diagnostic accuracy: Changing the paradigm?," *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, vol. 8, no. 8, 2019, doi: 10.3390/jcm8081217.
- [6] J. A. Johannigman, R. D. Branson, D. J. Johnson, K. Davis, and J. M. Hurst, "Out-of-hospital ventilation: bag-valve device vs transport ventilator," *Academic Emergency Medicine*, vol. 2, no. 8, pp. 719–724, 1995, doi: 10.1111/j.1553-2712.1995.tb03624.x.
- [7] A. Vasan *et al.*, "MADVent: A low-cost ventilator for patients with COVID-19," *Medical Devices & Sensors*, vol. 3, no. 4, 2020, doi: 10.1002/mds3.10106.
- [8] M. J. Ghafour, M. Naseem, F. Ilyas, M. S. Sarfaraz, M. I. Ali, and A. Ejaz, "Prototyping of a cost effective and portable ventilator," *ICIEECT 2017 - International Conference on Innovations in Electrical Engineering and Computational Technologies 2017, Proceedings*, 2017, doi: 10.1109/ICIEECT.2017.7916539.
- [9] P. Subha Hency Jose, P. Rajalakshmy, P. Manimegalai, and K. Rajasekaran, "A novel methodology for the design of a portable ventilator," *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 4785–4789, 2019, doi: 10.35940/ijtee.A5056.119119.
- [10] Z. L. Chen, Z. Y. Hu, and H. De Dai, "Control system design for a continuous positive airway pressure ventilator," *BioMedical Engineering Online*, vol. 11, 2012, doi: 10.1186/1475-925X-11-5.
- [11] A. Mohsen Al Hussein, H. Ju Lee, J. Negrete, S. Powelson, A. Tepper Servi, and A. H. Slocum, "Design and prototyping of a low-cost portable mechanical ventilator," *Journal of Medical Devices, Transactions of the ASME*, vol. 4, no. 2, p. 1, 2010, doi: 10.1115/1.3442790.
- [12] S. Kluge and J. Grensemann, "Methodik," *Deutsches Arzteblatt International*, vol. 115, no. 27–28, pp. 455–462, 2018, doi: 10.3238/arztebl.2018.0455.
- [13] A. Yadav, A. Kumar, and S. Sarkar, "Determination of standard oxygen transfer rate in venturi aeration system," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 1017, no. 1, 2021, doi: 10.1088/1757-899X/1017/1/012005.
- [14] A. D'Ausilio, "Arduino: A low-cost multipurpose lab equipment," *Behavior Research Methods*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 305–313, 2012, doi: 10.3758/s13428-011-0163-z.
- [15] C. Schäfle and C. Kautz, "Student reasoning in hydrodynamics: Bernoulli's principle versus the continuity equation," *Physical Review Physics Education Research*, vol. 17, no. 1, 2021, doi: 10.1103/PhysRevPhysEducRes.17.010147.
- [16] E. Schena, C. Massaroni, P. Saccomandi, and S. Cecchini, "Flow measurement in mechanical ventilation: A review," *Medical Engineering & Physics*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 257–264, Mar. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.medengphy.2015.01.010.
- [17] J. Alan *et al.*, "A Low-cost Air Flow Sensor/transducer for Medical Applications: Design and Experimental Characterization," *preprints.org*, 2021, doi: 10.20944/preprints202101.0404.v1.
- [18] P. M. and K. Dutt, "Review on speed control of DC motor using PI and PI fuzzy logic controller," *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*, 2021.
- [19] A. Singh, Dipraj, D. Singh, and A. Yadav, "FLC based speed control of Induction Motor," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 2007, no. 1, 2021, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/2007/1/012020.
- [20] H. Maghfiroh, M. Ahmad, A. Ramelan, and F. Adriyanto, "Fuzzy-PID in BLDC motor speed control using MATLAB/Simulink," *Journal of Robotics and Control (JRC)*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 8–13, 2022, doi: 10.18196/jrc.v3i1.10964.
- [21] D. J. Putra, N. Nofriadi, and E. Erlinda, "Implementation of fuzzy logic using Mamdani method to determine the quantity of bag production (case study in Roman Indah Padang bag factory)," *JURNAL TEKNOLOGI DAN OPEN SOURCE*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1–7, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.36378/jtos.v5i1.2220.
- [22] M. Irfan, C. N. Alam, and D. Tresna, "Implementation of fuzzy Mamdani logic method for student drop out status analytics," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1363, no. 1, 2019, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1363/1/012056.
- [23] A. Fernández and F. Herrera, "Linguistic fuzzy rules in data mining: Follow-up Mamdani fuzzy modeling principle," pp. 103–122, 2012, doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-24666-1_8.
- [24] S. K. Yadav, "DC motor position control using fuzzy proportional-derivative controllers with different defuzzification methods," *IOSR Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 37–47, 2015, doi: 10.9790/1676-10133747.
- [25] I. H. Usoro, U. T. Itaketo, and M. A. Umoren, "Control of a dc motor using fuzzy logic control algorithm," *Nigerian Journal of Technology*, vol. 36, no. 2, p. 594, 2017, doi: 10.4314/njt.v36i2.35.

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